

PACIFICUS

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“A FARMERS’ CHILD”

You plow the soil
And so their seeds
You love your toil
We admire your deeds

You are extraordinary
You work all day
At the peak of a sunny day
You make yourself busy

Hard work bears fruit
You always remind us
Though you need to sweat
Harvest is truly sweet

You are our father
We are your children
You are our provider
Our greatest defender

Of all that you have sowed
We will always be the best that you reap
I'm a child of farmers
And I am proud about it

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